

One-dimensional CNN-based classification of fine hand movements using low-spatial-resolution sEMG

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Abstract— The control of myoelectric prostheses to perform fine finger movements represents a significant challenge in rehabilitation engineering, especially when using a reduced number of surface electromyography (sEMG) channels to ensure the clinical viability of the device. This work proposes and evaluates the performance of a one-dimensional Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture for the classification of seven fine hand gestures from sEMG data acquired with a low-spatial-resolution system of only three channels. Data were collected from five healthy volunteers, pre-processed through filtering and overlapping windowing, and used to train the model. The CNN achieved a mean validation accuracy of $96.46\% \pm 1.31\%$, demonstrating high efficacy and robustness against inter-subject variability. The result indicates that the deep learning approach can extract discriminative features from complex sEMG signals, even with limited spatial information, presenting itself as a high-performance and clinically viable solution for the development of more accessible and intuitive prosthetic control systems.

Keywords— Convolutional Neural Networks, Surface Electromyography, Myoelectric Prostheses, Gesture Classification, Fine Movements.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years, research on myoelectric prosthesis control has taken on a prominent role in rehabilitation engineering. The focus has been on creating devices with increasingly intuitive control and multiple degrees of freedom (DoFs), designed to restore functional hand movements for individuals with upper-limb amputations [1]. Among the various challenges in this field, accurately classifying fine finger motions stands out. These small, precise movements—such as gripping a cup, writing, or handling small objects—are fundamental to daily activities and directly influence the autonomy and quality of life of prosthesis users [2].

A widely adopted approach for enabling such control relies on surface electromyography (sEMG), a technique capable of decoding the user's motor intent. By placing electrodes on the skin, it is possible to record the electrical activity generated during muscle contractions. This method, well established in both research and clinical environments, is valued for being non-invasive and reliable in translating neuromuscular commands [3][4][5].

Still, moving from laboratory prototypes to clinically viable systems is far from trivial. sEMG is a non-stationary signal, meaning its statistical properties can change over time—whether due to muscle fatigue, individual physiological differences, or even slight electrode shifts [2]. When dealing with fine movements, the challenge becomes more pronounced: muscle activations are weaker, and signals from neighboring muscles often overlap, resulting in patterns with low separability.

A further difficulty lies in balancing performance with practicality. For a prosthesis to be both accessible and comfortable, using fewer electrodes is preferable. This simplifies setup and reduces discomfort for the user but inevitably lowers spatial resolution, limiting the amount of muscle activity detail available. The literature often notes that increasing the number of channels is among the most effective ways to boost pattern discriminability and classification accuracy [3].

Historically, improvements in classification have come from pairing manual feature engineering with classical machine learning. Typically, features are extracted—often from the time domain, as in the well-known Hudgins set—due to their simplicity and low computational demand [6]. These features are then used to train a classifier. However, when the signals are complex or the system has low resolution, the performance hinges heavily on the hand-crafted features, which can create a significant bottleneck [7].

In recent years, deep learning methods such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been explored as a way to bypass these limitations. CNNs adopt an end-to-end learning strategy, automatically identifying relevant features directly from raw or pre-processed sEMG inputs [8]. This provides flexibility and the ability to capture intricate patterns that traditional methods might miss, with promising results already reported in biomedical contexts [9].

Within this framework, the present work introduces a one-dimensional CNN aimed at classifying seven fine hand gestures. The goal is to test this approach under the dual constraint of complex fine-movement recognition and a low-spatial-resolution setup, using sEMG data from only three channels. We assess its accuracy, robustness to inter-subject variability, and inference latency, aiming to show that CNNs can be a practical, high-performance solution for developing more accessible myoelectric prostheses.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Acquisition and Experimental Protocol

Five healthy volunteers, aged between 24 and 30, took part in this study. Data collection was conducted at the Biomedical Engineering Laboratory (BioLab) of the Federal University of Uberlândia (UFU), with prior informed consent from all participants.

For acquisition, the Myosystem Br1-P84 electromyograph (DataHominis Tec Ltda) was used, with a sampling rate of 2 kHz. Three active electrodes, connected in a differential configuration, were positioned to record the sEMG signals. The integrated preamplifier was set to a gain of 20×, ensuring high rejection of common-mode interference, including 60 Hz power-line noise.

Electrode placement followed an adapted version of Zipp's (1982) protocol [10]. They were positioned transversely on the forearm, targeting the Flexor Digitorum Superficialis, Flexor Carpi Ulnaris, and Extensor Digitorum

muscles.

Fig. 1 Cross-section, positioning of electrodes on the forearm.

The experimental protocol included seven distinct motor tasks, all representing fine, functionally relevant movements: individual flexion of each of the five fingers, a pinch grip, and a tripod grip. To standardize contractions, participants were asked to perform each task while holding a small rubber ball. Each movement was executed in six blocks of ten repetitions, with each contraction lasting three seconds, followed by a three-second rest period. An audiovisual cue synchronized with a trigger signal guided the timing and ensured alignment with the acquisition system.

Fig. 2 Representation of the tasks defined for the experimental protocol..

B. Data Pre-processing

After acquisition, the raw signals underwent a pre-processing pipeline. A 4th-order Butterworth band-pass filter (20–500 Hz) was applied first, followed by a notch filter to remove 60 Hz interference and its harmonics. Using

the trigger markers, 3.2-second windows were extracted for each contraction, isolating the segments containing the motor events of interest.

To increase the number of training samples, we applied overlapping window segmentation. Each segment was divided into 200 ms windows with an 80% overlap, corresponding to a 40 ms step. This resulted in 33,572 individual samples per subject for the seven-class classification task.

Finally, the data were normalized channel-wise using the Z-score method. For each channel, the mean and standard deviation were calculated from all training data points and applied to both training and validation sets. The final pre-processed dataset took the form of a 3D tensor with dimensions (N, 400, 3), where N is the number of samples, 400 is the number of time points per window, and 3 is the number of sEMG channels. This preserved the spatial-temporal structure of the signals for CNN processing.

Fig. 3 Flowchart of preprocessing of sEMG signals.

C. Data Processing

Classification was performed using a one-dimensional CNN designed specifically for temporal signal analysis. The dataset was split into 80% for training and 20% for validation, using a fixed random seed to ensure reproducibility.

The network architecture had two main parts:

1. Feature extraction body – three sequential convolutional blocks. Each block consisted of convolution, batch normalization, ReLU activation, max pooling (halving the feature map size), and dropout for regularization. The dropout rate was 0.15 in all convolutional blocks. The number of filters increased and kernel size decreased across blocks to progressively capture more complex features.

Block 1: 64 filters, kernel size 11

Block 2: 128 filters, kernel size 9

Block 3: 256 filters, kernel size 7

2. Classification head – the extracted features were flattened and passed to a dense layer with 128 neurons, followed by dropout at a rate of 0.4. The output layer contained seven neurons with a softmax activation, producing class probability distributions.

The model was trained using the Adam optimizer (initial learning rate: 0.001) with categorical cross-entropy loss. Training was capped at 50 epochs with a batch size of 64. Two strategies were used to prevent overfitting:

- Early stopping: training stopped if validation accuracy failed to improve after seven epochs, restoring the best weights.
- Learning rate scheduling: the learning rate was reduced if validation loss plateaued.

The final evaluation was performed on the validation set using the best restored model weights.

Fig. 4 Proposed CNN Architecture.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance of the proposed CNN architecture was assessed in terms of classification accuracy and robustness to inter-subject variability. All results reported here represent the average performance across the five volunteers for the task of classifying seven fine hand movements.

Overall, the model’s performance in classifying the seven defined movement patterns, summarized in Table 1, shows that the architecture was highly effective. The approach reached a mean validation accuracy of $96.46\% \pm 1.31\%$, a figure consistent with state-of-the-art results for a similar number of gestures, such as the $\sim 97.9\%$ reported by Côté-Allard et al. (2016). This high accuracy also agrees with the observation by Atzori et al. (2016) that, in studies with fewer than ten classes, values above 90% are generally

expected. The difference between training accuracy (99.21%) and validation accuracy (96.46%) was 2.75%, suggesting a mild and well-controlled level of overfitting—a behavior that is often seen in high-capacity networks that specialize on the training set to achieve greater predictive power.

Table 3 – Detailed CNN Classifier Performance for 7 Classes

CNN			
Volunteer	Training Accuracy	Validation Accuracy	Difference
1	99,30%	98,17%	1,13%
2	98,66%	95,50%	3,16%
3	99,40%	97,24%	2,16%
4	99,22%	96,57%	2,65%
5	99,48%	94,82%	4,66%
Mean ± SD	99,21% ± 0,32%	96,46% ± 1,31%	2,75% ± 1,30%

One of the most relevant findings of this study is the model’s robustness to inter-subject variability. The low standard deviation ($\pm 1.31\%$) indicates that the CNN maintained high and consistent performance across different users. This is particularly noteworthy given that the acquisition setup employed only three sEMG channels. As noted in the literature, such as in the review by Oskoei and Hu (2007), increasing the number of channels is often considered one of the most effective ways to improve classification accuracy. The fact that the CNN achieved such high and stable performance with low spatial resolution is therefore a remarkable result, pointing to the architecture’s ability to extract useful and discriminative information from a limited dataset.

To further illustrate these results, Figure 5 presents the confusion matrix for a representative volunteer. The matrix shows a clearly dominant main diagonal, with low and scattered misclassification rates. This reinforces the CNN’s strong discriminative capability, even for gestures that are functionally similar, such as “Pinch” and “Tripod.”

Fig. 4 CNN Confusion Matrix volunteer 3.

This high level of performance, however, comes at the cost of a considerably greater computational demand during model training—an inherent characteristic of deep learning architectures. Even so, once the network was trained, its inference latency proved to be fully compatible with the real-time control requirements of myoelectric prostheses.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study validated the effectiveness of the proposed one-dimensional CNN for classifying seven fine hand movements using a low-resolution sEMG acquisition setup with only three channels. The results showed high performance, with a mean validation accuracy of $96.46\% \pm 1.31\%$, and notable robustness to inter-subject variability. Achieving such performance with a small number of channels is particularly significant, as it demonstrates the network’s ability to extract discriminative information from a limited dataset—representing an advance over approaches that rely on larger electrode arrays to reach high accuracy.

While training demands greater computational resources, the model’s inference speed meets the requirements for real-time control. Taken together, these findings indicate that the proposed CNN is both a high-performance and practical solution for developing more accessible and user-friendly myoelectric prostheses.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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